

Revealing the Subjective Well-Being of Female Farmers in Terms of the Existence of Social Support in Songan a Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to find out how social support influence the subjective well-being of female farmers in Songan A village, Kintamani district, Bangli regency. This research is to find out the casualty between independent variable that is social support with subjective well-being as dependent variable. The subject that used in this study is the female farmers in Songan village with 110 populations. The data collected by contributing questionnaires and then analyzed by using simple linear regression. The result of this study showed there is an influence of social support to the subjective well-being of female farmers in Songan village, Kintamani district, Bangli regency. It means the more female farmers get social support, the more prosperous their life will be

KEYWORDS: Social Support; Subjective Well-Being; Bali

I. INTRODUCTION

Most of the people living in rural areas have their main livelihood as farmers. In general, agriculture is a human activity in farming, livestock, fisheries and forestry (Achmad Zaini, 2019). The purpose of agricultural activities is to sustain the life of rural communities, most of which are carried out by the head of the household, namely the man with the assistance of his wife. They have the same portion and cooperate in carrying out their work such as cultivating agricultural land, planting seeds, irrigation, fertilizing, spraying, harvesting and marketing so that this proves that women have a balanced role with men in agriculture (Syafa'at & Djauhar P, 2017)

The role of men is to make a living, in this case what is meant is farming, while women play a role in taking care of household work and their children. Work as housewives is done voluntarily by women and household food security depends on the role of women to obtain economic resources (Dwiastuti, 2017). However, at this time women not only have a role as housewives but also have a role in contributing to income by working as farmers, in addition to experiencing rapid development in the field of agriculture, women are also able to act as managers and make decisions on the farming business they live (Asriyanti Syarif, 2017).

The success of women in agriculture and completing every household work can in fact provide opportunities for women to contribute to agricultural development, especially in rural areas. Agriculture is a way out that is used to improve the state budget and open up job or business opportunities for women because women are the center point of the economy. The involvement of women in agriculture is very important. Agriculture can be a driving force for development and poverty reduction to achieve prosperity (Rajam, 2020). Although women's access to information and education to deal with future problems is still relatively low, women continue to carry out their work as farmers to meet their daily needs (Arsanti, 2013). Women have been involved and play an active role in agricultural businesses by being directly involved in land management, seed selection, selection of facilities and marketing. The broadening of the role of women is able to improve the position of women compared to the position of men as workers in the agricultural sector.

In addition to having income contributions through agriculture, women are also able to become housewives who complete every housework. Women have the authority and expertise in managing the household and managing finances in daily life. Although the role of women in agriculture is no longer in doubt, in reality the condition of women farmers is often not visible in agricultural development activities and women's participation in training programs is still relatively low (Asriyanti Syarif, 2017).

Revealing the Subjective Well-Being of Female Farmers in Terms of the Existence of Social Support in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency

Growth in the agricultural sector will be followed by an increase in welfare and vice versa, if there is a decline in the agricultural sector it will affect the decrease in the level of welfare (Sambari Halim Radianto, 2020).

In a study of subjective well-being, women tend to have more experience and mood than men (Haug, 2007). Subjective well-being is defined as happiness and comfort obtained through evaluation of events that have been experienced. Subjective well-being focuses on positive experiences and satisfaction with one's life (Diener et al., 2015). In line with opinion (Cummins et al., 2011) states that subjective well-being is a positive assessment in a life. Subjective well-being focuses on positive experiences and satisfaction with one's life. Someone who has subjective well-being is able to think creatively, is optimistic, works hard, is not easily discouraged, and also has more smiles and joy when compared to someone who claims to be unhappy who says that subjective well-being is a positive assessment in a life. Subjective well-being focuses on positive experiences and satisfaction with one's life. Someone who has subjective well-being is able to think creatively, is optimistic, works hard, is not easily discouraged, and also has more smiles and joy when compared to someone who claims to be unhappy (Agustini & Nurhidayah, 2012). There are two subjective well-being theories, namely bottom-up theories and top-down theories, bottom-up theories view that happiness can be felt by a person depending on the small happiness that can be obtained through a collection of happy events experienced, so that happiness is part of subjective well-being. Subjective well-being is a positive experience that occurs in a person's life, they will get happiness if they experience many pleasant events. This theory assumes that, to improve subjective well-being, a person needs to change the situation and environment that can affect his life experience. While the top down theories view subjective well-being that has been experienced by a person very much depends on the way the individual evaluates or assesses all events experienced with a positive point of view. A person's subjective well-being is determined by the individual himself, whether the events experienced are able to create prosperity or not. This theory considers people's attitudes and ways of interpreting the events they experience (Compton, 2013; Putri, 2016).

Factors Affecting Subjective Well-Being are self-esteem, sense of awareness control, openness, optimism, meaning and purpose in life, social support, extra version & neuroticism, self-confidence, gender differences, goals, income, marriage, religion, enjoyment of life, intensity of positive experiences and intelligence in good relations (Compton, 2013).

To achieve subjective well-being, it is necessary to have social support from various parties such as family, friends, and other closest people. Social support is providing information to other people either directly or indirectly by providing behavioral assistance to giving in the form of material, this is obtained from close social relationships. Social support does not only provide assistance to others but involves the recipient's perception of the assistance that has been given, so social support is very important to be developed (Ahyani, 2012). For example, if an individual is having a problem they really need motivation, encouragement and support from others to get out of the problem he is facing (Tarigan, 2018).

Social support is the most powerful factor influencing subjective well-being. A person will get subjective well-being if he gets high social support from family, closest people and friends or friends (Compton, 2013).

Songan A Village is located in Bangli Regency which is a highland and is one of the most strategic areas for the agricultural sector so that the majority of the population works in agriculture. Based on Songan A Village Statistics (2019), the number of female farmers/planters is more than the number of male farmers/planters. With a total comparison of 19.16% compared to 19.76%. This data shows one of the advantages for women compared to men. Although in essence the responsibility of a man is to work and try to earn a living to meet the needs of himself and the rest of the family besides agriculture is one of the activities to earn income to meet family needs which is identical to the role of a man as the head of the family (Asriyanti Syarif, 2017). Despite the fact that the attitudes and efforts to fulfill the needs that have been carried out have not had an impact on the welfare of women, especially women. The low contribution of women in efforts to improve welfare is a reflection that so far the role of women in the economy has not been taken into account. Programs created by the government to alleviate poverty tend to widen social inequality, this is because the policies made by the government tend to be specifically for men, even though work in agriculture is predominantly done by women.

Meanwhile, the education of female farmers in Songan A Village is still dominated by elementary education level. In relation to health facilities, it can also be categorized as lacking, this is indicated by the presence of residents who do not have health facilities in the availability of latrines. As well as social conditions are also still relatively low, because basically the problem of lighting is not a problem in social life in Bali but in Songan A Village there are still people who have not been able to enjoy electricity facilities as a means of lighting as many as 411 people they only use kerosene as a means of lighting. So this condition shows that the welfare of farmers in Songan A Village is still low (BPS, 2020). This proves that the welfare of women farmers is still lacking which can be measured by measuring health, economic conditions, happiness, security, peace and quality of life (Abdhal, 2012).

Revealing the Subjective Well-Being of Female Farmers in Terms of the Existence of Social Support in Songan a Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency

The lack of welfare of women farmers does not discourage women farmers from working, they think that the work environment is an interesting, fun and full of challenges. The large number of women who want to work as farmers is due to the social support obtained from their families and the government. The results of initial observations made by researchers found the problem that the average contribution of women's income was only 37.27% (BPS, 2020). The low contribution of women in the family economy is a reflection that so far the role of women in the economy has not been taken into account. In fact, if seen from BPS data, the number of women working in agriculture is higher than the number of men. The lack of welfare of women farmers does not discourage women farmers from working, they think that the work environment is an interesting, fun and full of challenges. The large number of women who want to work as farmers is due to the social support obtained from their families and the government.

Based on the description above, it is necessary to conduct research related to female farmers in Songan A Village with the aim of knowing the effect of social support on the subjective welfare of female farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency.

II. METHOD

This study uses a causal research design that describes a causal relationship between social support variables and subjective well-being variables for female farmers. The location of this research is Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency. The population used is all female farmers in Songan A Village located in Kintamani District, Bangli Regency, the number of samples used is 110 people. Techniques in collecting data using interview instruments and questionnaires with simple regression analysis data analysis techniques that have passed the regression prerequisite test.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The results of the statistical test of the effect of social support on the subjective welfare of female farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency can be seen in the t test using a significance level of 5% with the results of the t count value of 5.258 and t table of 1.65909 so that $t \text{ count} > t \text{ table}$ ($5.258 > 1.65909$) with a significance level of $p\text{-value } 0.000 < = 0.05$. This shows that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted, which means that there is an influence of social support on the subjective welfare of women farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency which can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Simple Regression Analysis

<i>Model</i>		<i>Unstandardized Coefficients</i>		<i>Standardized Coefficients</i>	<i>t</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
		<i>B</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Beta</i>		
1	(Constant)	29.562	6.413		4.610	0,005
	Dukungan Sosial	0.924	0.176	0.451	5.258	0,000

Source: SPSS output

Based on the explanation above, it can be seen that there is an influence between social support on the subjective welfare of female farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency. So that with the amount of social assistance obtained, female farmers will get prosperity and create happiness. The social support obtained by farmers from the closest people to the government in the form of the Field Extension Program (PPL), is able to provide enthusiasm and a sense of appreciation so that they feel comfortable working as farmers. This is in line with research (Putri, 2016; Sulastri & Hartoyo, 2014). A person will get subjective well-being if he gets high social support from family, closest people and friends or friends, it will increase emotional intelligence. Social support is also one of the most consistent and very strong factors in influencing subjective well-being (Compton, 2013).

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that there is an effect of social support on subjective well-being. This result is supported by the large percentage who choose the answer strongly agree on each variable that is equal to 59% and 63%. It can be seen that social support is also a very important and much needed assistance by female farmers in Songan A Village, this assistance can be in the form of tangible assistance such as providing care and empathy so that those concerned get emotional benefits in the form of feeling comfortable, loved, appreciated, cared for, calmness and increase self-confidence. With the high social support obtained by women farmers, it will have an impact on their subjective well-being.

Revealing the Subjective Well-Being of Female Farmers in Terms of the Existence of Social Support in Songan a Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency

IV. CONCLUSION RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In line with the research objectives that have been explained, namely wanting to know the effect of social support on the subjective welfare of women farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency and paying attention to the results of the analysis that have been reviewed in Chapter IV, it is concluded that there is an effect of social support on the subjective welfare of women farmers in Songan A Village, Kintamani District, Bangli Regency.

Based on the results of the discussion in the research, it can be seen that social support is a factor that affects subjective well-being. If the social support obtained is high, such as caring, empathy, attention to worry, this will provide emotional support to the person concerned. The female farmers in Songan A Village will get comfort, happiness, feel valued and get recognition. Of course the support that has been given will have an impact on the subjective well-being of women farmers will give a positive assessment of all the events they experience as a result of the feeling of comfort and happiness they get from social support.

Based on the conclusions that can be explained, several suggestions are put forward as consideration for women farmers and for other researchers in the future, namely to female farmers in Songan A Village, Bangli District, Bangli Regency, it is suggested to be able to manage the finances obtained from the benefits of farming. Aims to improve welfare which can be seen in terms of income including paying attention to the availability of latrines, electricity, to education which is still dominated by elementary schools. It is also advisable to appreciate any kind of assistance provided by the government or family. Thus the assistance obtained will run optimally. For further researchers to be more able to research maximally related to other factors that can affect subjective well-being.

REFERENCES

- 1) Abdhul, W. G. dkk. (2012). *Interkoneksi Islam dan Kesejahteraan Sosial*. Samudra Biru.
- 2) Achmad Zaini. (2019). *Nilai Tambah Dan Daya Saing Produk Unggulan Di Kutai Barat*. Depublish.
- 3) Agustini, R., & Nurhidayah, S. (2012). Kebahagiaan Lansia Ditinjau Dari Dukungan Sosial dan Spiritualitas. *Jurnal Soul*, 5, 15–32.
- 4) Ahyani, fani kumalasari dan latifah nur. (2012). *Hubungan Antara Dukungan Sosial Dengan Penyesuaian Diri Remaja Di Panti Asuhan Latifah Nur Ahyani*. 1(1).
- 5) Arsanti, T. A. (2013). Perempuan dan Pembangunan Sektor Pertanian. *Jurnal Maksipreneur: Manajemen, Koperasi, Dan Entrepreneurship*, 3(1), 63. <https://doi.org/10.30588/jmp.v3i1.88>
- 6) Asriyanti Syarif, M. Z. (2017). *Intisari Sosiologi Pertanian*. CV. Inti Media Tama.
- 7) BPS. (2020). *Tingkat Pendidikan Petani*. Badan Pusat Statistik. <https://doi.org/https://www.bps.go.id/subject/6/tenaga-kerja.html#subjekViewTab3>
- 8) Compton, W. C. dan E. H. (2013). *Positive Psychology The Science of Happiness and Flourishing Second Edition* (2nd ed.).
- 9) Cummins, R. A., Lau, A. L. D., Davey, G., & McGillivray, J. (2011). *Measuring Subjective Wellbeing : The Personal Wellbeing Index – Intellectual Measuring Subjective Wellbeing : The Personal Wellbeing Index – Intellectual Disability*. February 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-90-481-9650-0>
- 10) Diener, E., Oishi, S., & Lucas, R. E. (2015). National accounts of subjective well-being. *American Psychologist*, 70(3), 234–242. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0038899>
- 11) Dwiastuti, R. (2017). Metode Penelitian Sosial Ekonomi Pertanian. *Aegaeum Journal*, 8(4).
- 12) Haug, M. (2007). *Kemiskinan dan Desentralisasi di Kutai Barat*. Center For International Forestry Research.
- 13) Putri, D. R. (2016). Peran Dukungan Sosial dan Kecerdasan Emosi Terhadap Kesejahteraan Subjektif pada Remaja Awal. *Indigenous: Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi*, 1(1), 12. <https://doi.org/10.23917/indigenous.v1i1.1770>
- 14) Rajam, G. S. (2020). Agriculture Sektore: A Study on Challenges and Role of Women. *Aegaeum Journal*, 8(4).
- 15) Sambari Halim Radianto. (2020). *Pertanian dan Industri*. Kencana.
- 16) Sulastri, S., & Hartoyo. (2014). Effect of Social Support and Livelihood Strategies on Subjective Well-Being of Family at Retirement Age Abstract. *Jur. Ilm. Kel. & Kons.*, 7(2), 83–92.
- 17) Syaifa'at, N., & Djauhar P, A. (2017). Identifikasi Penyebab Rendahnya Penyalur Kredit Usahatani. *Pusat Penelitian Sosial Ekonomi Pertanian*, 113–119.
- 18) Tarigan, M. (2018). Hubungan Dukungan Sosial dengan Subjective Well-Being pada Remaja yang Memiliki Orangtua Tunggal. *Jurnal Diversita*, 4(1), 1. <https://doi.org/10.31289/diversita.v4i1.1565>